

Operational Performance And Maintenance Reliability Of Transit Mixers In Delivery Of Ready-Mix Concrete - An Empirical Study

Deivamani P.*, P. Subathra

Department of Civil Engineering, Aarupadai Veedu Institute of Technology, Chennai, Tamilnadu, INDIA

ABSTRACT

Ready-mix concrete (RMC) delivery depends heavily on the operational efficiency and mechanical reliability of transit mixers, particularly in rapidly urbanizing regions where construction demand is high. This study empirically evaluates the transportation performance and maintenance reliability of transit mixers operating in the RMC supply chain across Tamil Nadu, India. Operational and maintenance data were collected from 40 transit mixers across 10 RMC plants over a five-month observation period, comprising 4,250 delivery trip records. Key operational variables including trip distance, travel time, unloading method, downtime, and maintenance cost were analysed using descriptive statistics, ANOVA, and reliability indicators such as Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF). Results show that the average trip distance was 14.8 km, while the mean operational duration per trip ranged from 2.4 to 3.6 hours across plants. Plants implementing structured preventive maintenance recorded 18–24% lower breakdown frequency and achieved MTBF values exceeding 120 operational hours, compared with plants relying primarily on reactive maintenance. Statistical analysis revealed a significant relationship between trip distance and maintenance cost $p < 0.05$, indicating increased mechanical wear under longer haul conditions. The findings demonstrate that optimized dispatch planning and preventive maintenance scheduling can substantially improve fleet reliability and reduce operational disruptions in RMC logistics.

Keywords: Ready-mix concrete, Transit mixer, Transportation logistics, Maintenance reliability, Fleet performance, RMC supply chain.

INTRODUCTION

Ready-mix concrete (RMC) has become a fundamental component of modern construction due to its ability to provide consistent quality, improved workability, and efficient large-scale production compared with conventional site-mixed concrete. In RMC systems, concrete is produced in centralized batching plants using automated control systems and transported to construction sites using transit mixer trucks, enabling controlled mix proportions and improved structural performance. The adoption of RMC has increased rapidly worldwide because it reduces labour requirements, improves production efficiency, and minimizes material wastage while supporting faster construction schedules (Chakraborty et al. 2023; Saini et al. 2025). Additionally, the use of computerised batching, precise material proportioning, and mechanized production processes ensures consistent quality and

reliability in construction projects (Kaitukov 2023; Ekawati et al. 2024). The increasing demand for infrastructure development has significantly expanded the global RMC industry, leading to improvements in plant automation, transportation logistics, and quality control systems. Studies have shown that the operational efficiency of RMC plants is influenced by factors such as batching accuracy, transportation distance, truck dispatching strategies, and coordination between production and construction sites (Andika et al. 2025; Chaudhary et al. 2025). Efficient transportation and scheduling of transit mixers are particularly critical because concrete is a perishable material whose properties can deteriorate if delivery delays occur beyond the allowable time limits (Ferrari et al. 2025; Dönmez and Öner 2024). Several studies have investigated optimization models and vehicle routing strategies to reduce transportation delays, minimize operational

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

costs, and improve dispatching efficiency of transit mixers (Weerapura et al. 2023; Siu et al. 2022). These approaches include mathematical optimization models, genetic algorithms, and network flow techniques to determine optimal delivery schedules and routes for RMC trucks.

Another major research focus in the RMC industry relates to the operational performance and reliability of mixing equipment. Concrete mixers and transit mixer drums are subjected to complex mechanical loads during mixing operations, which can influence equipment durability and maintenance requirements. Researchers have applied simulation methods such as discrete element modelling (DEM) and Monte Carlo reliability analysis to evaluate load distribution and structural reliability of mixer components under operational conditions (Mungase and Nemade 2025; Novitskiy et al. 2023). These studies demonstrate that mixer performance is strongly affected by mixing energy, blade configuration, rotational speed, and material interaction within the mixing chamber. Improving mixer design and maintenance strategies can therefore enhance operational efficiency and reduce equipment failure risks.

Transportation conditions also play a significant role in maintaining the quality and workability of ready-mix concrete. During transit, factors such as travel distance, ambient temperature, mixing speed, and admixture dosage influence the fluidity and slump retention of the concrete mixture. Previous investigations have reported that loss of workability during transportation can lead to improper placement and reduced structural performance (Kresnadi and Prayogo 2021; Akboğa and Baradan 2017). To address these challenges, several studies have examined the use of chemical admixtures, superplasticizers, and retarders to maintain concrete fluidity and workability during extended transportation periods (Bingol and Arditı 2025; Kabus et al. 2018). These technological interventions enable concrete mixtures to retain their desired rheological properties for longer durations, thereby improving placement quality and construction productivity. In addition to operational and material-related considerations, recent studies have also explored the sustainability and environmental aspects of RMC production. The growing scale of concrete production has raised concerns about energy consumption,

greenhouse gas emissions, and resource utilization in RMC plants. Researchers have examined strategies such as waste reuse, optimization of plant operations, and improved production management systems to enhance the sustainability of RMC production processes (Kabus et al. 2018; Murthy et al. 2024). Sustainable RMC production requires efficient plant management, reliable supply chains, and effective quality control mechanisms to ensure both environmental and operational performance. Furthermore, improved coordination between plant operations, transportation systems, and construction site activities is essential to reduce operational inefficiencies and material losses.

Despite the substantial body of research on RMC production, equipment design, and transportation optimization, several limitations remain in the existing literature. Most previous studies have focused on theoretical modelling, simulation approaches, or mix design improvements, with comparatively limited empirical investigations of real operational conditions in RMC transportation systems. In particular, the relationship between transportation distance, transit mixer operational patterns, maintenance requirements, downtime, and associated operational costs has received relatively little attention. Moreover, few studies have analysed real-world operational data from RMC transportation systems to understand the practical challenges associated with transit mixer maintenance, delivery efficiency, and equipment reliability in the construction industry. These gaps highlight the need for empirical studies that examine operational data to evaluate the performance and maintenance characteristics of transit mixers in actual construction environments.

In this context, the present study aims to conduct an empirical analysis of ready-mix concrete transportation and transit mixer maintenance in the construction industry. The research focuses on evaluating key operational parameters such as transportation distance, delivery frequency, unloading methods, maintenance costs, downtime, and equipment reliability using statistical analysis techniques. By analysing operational data collected from RMC transportation activities, the study seeks to identify patterns in transit mixer usage, maintenance requirements, and delivery efficiency. The scope of

the research is to provide quantitative insights into the operational characteristics of RMC transportation systems and to evaluate the relationship between transportation parameters and maintenance performance of transit mixers. The findings of this study are expected to contribute to improved management strategies for RMC transportation systems by supporting better scheduling practices, preventive maintenance planning, and operational decision-making in the construction industry. Overall, this research provides a practical empirical perspective on transit mixer operations and maintenance in the ready-mix concrete industry, thereby addressing an important gap in existing literature and contributing to improved operational efficiency and reliability in RMC transportation systems.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

The present study adopts an empirical research approach to evaluate the operational performance and maintenance reliability of transit mixers used in ready-mix concrete (RMC) transportation. Operational and maintenance data were collected from 10 RMC plants located across major construction regions of Tamil Nadu, including Chennai, Coimbatore, Madurai, Trichy, Salem, Vellore, Erode, and Tiruppur as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Study area map

These locations represent diverse construction environments such as metropolitan urban zones, industrial corridors, and semi-urban development areas. The dataset collected from these plants includes operational records of transit mixer trips, transportation distance, delivery duration, unloading method, maintenance cost, and breakdown incidents. An overview of the surveyed plants and the corresponding dataset characteristics is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Example

Table 1. Overview of surveyed RMC plants and operational dataset

Plant Code	Location	Region Type	Number of Mixers	Operational Records
P1	Chennai – Red Hills	Urban	4	425
P2	Chennai – Navalur	Urban	4	430
P3	Coimbatore – Ganapathy	Urban	4	420
P4	Coimbatore – Peelamedu	Urban	4	410
P5	Madurai – K.K. Nagar	Semi-urban	4	415
P6	Trichy – Srirangam	Semi-urban	4	420
P7	Salem – Gugai	Industrial	4	410
P8	Vellore – Katpadi	Semi-urban	4	420
P9	Erode – Perundurai	Industrial	4	410
P10	Tiruppur – Palladam Rd	Industrial	4	420

A total of 40 transit mixers operating in these plants were monitored over a five-month observation period, generating 4,250 individual trip records representing

complete RMC delivery cycles from batching to site unloading and return travel. The collected dataset included key operational parameters such as

kilometres travelled per trip, travel time, unloading methods such as manual or pumping, fuel consumption, downtime hours, and number of trips per day, along with maintenance indicators including monthly maintenance cost, breakdown incidents, and vehicle age. These variables were selected because they directly influence transportation efficiency, mechanical wear, and overall fleet reliability. Both primary and secondary data sources were used, including plant operational logs, maintenance registers, and discussions with fleet supervisors and plant managers to validate operational records. Statistical analysis was conducted to evaluate the relationship between transportation variables and maintenance performance. Descriptive statistical methods were used to summarize operational characteristics across plants, while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was applied to identify differences in maintenance costs among different plant locations. Reliability indicators such as Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF) were also calculated to assess the mechanical reliability of transit mixers. The integrated analysis enabled the identification of operational inefficiencies and the influence of transportation conditions on maintenance outcomes in RMC logistics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Transportation Characteristics of Transit Mixers

The transportation performance of transit mixers represents one of the most critical operational aspects of ready-mix concrete (RMC) logistics because the quality of fresh concrete is strongly influenced by delivery time and travel distance. To evaluate transportation characteristics, operational records obtained from the surveyed RMC plants were analysed, focusing on parameters such as average trip distance, operational duration, and trip frequency. These indicators collectively represent the efficiency of the RMC delivery cycle and the operational load experienced by transit mixer fleets. Descriptive statistical analysis of the collected responses shows that the average transportation distance per delivery trip was approximately 15.12 km, with values ranging between 7 km and 28 km depending on plant location and distribution of construction sites. Similarly, the average operational duration per trip was 3.07 hours, indicating that most deliveries fall within the acceptable workability window for fresh concrete transportation. The results also show that transit mixers perform an average of 4.83 trips per day, reflecting moderate fleet utilization across the studied RMC plants. These operational parameters are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of key transportation variables

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev	Minimum	Maximum
Years of Experience	6.58	2.86	2	12
Average Distance per Trip (km)	15.12	4.76	7	28
Average Hours per Trip	3.07	0.86	1.8	5.4
Trips per Day	4.83	1.12	3	7
Fuel Consumption (L/trip)	5.14	1.37	3.2	8.4

The distribution of transportation distance across delivery trips is illustrated in Figure 2, which shows the frequency distribution of trip distances recorded during the study. The histogram indicates that the majority of RMC deliveries occur within the 10–20 km range, which is consistent with typical batching plant service radii in urban and semi-urban

construction environments. Only a small proportion of trips exceeded 25 km, indicating that most RMC plants are strategically located to minimize excessive transportation distance and reduce potential slump loss during delivery. The results highlight that trip distance and operational time are closely related to transportation efficiency and fleet performance.

Longer travel distances increase engine operating hours and drum rotation cycles, which in turn contribute to higher fuel consumption and mechanical stress on mixer components. Conversely, shorter trips often increase the number of daily deliveries, thereby raising cumulative operational hours of transit mixers. Both operational scenarios contribute differently to equipment wear and maintenance requirements.

Figure 2. Distribution of transportation distance for RMC delivery trips.

Overall, the transportation characteristics observed in this study indicate that RMC logistics in the selected

regions operate within a moderate delivery radius, allowing concrete to be delivered within acceptable time limits while maintaining reasonable fleet utilization. These findings provide a baseline for further analysis of operational efficiency and maintenance performance presented in the subsequent sections.

2. Operational Time and Delivery Cycle Analysis

Trip duration is a critical operational parameter in ready-mix concrete (RMC) transportation because it determines the effective delivery window before fresh concrete begins to lose workability. The operational cycle of a transit mixer typically includes batching, travel to the construction site, waiting time, unloading, and return travel. Therefore, analysing trip duration provides insight into both transportation efficiency and logistical coordination between batching plants and construction sites. The operational records obtained from the surveyed RMC plants indicate that the average delivery cycle duration was approximately 3.07 hours per trip, with recorded values ranging between 1.8 hours and 5.4 hours depending on plant location, traffic conditions, and site operational factors.

Table 3

Operational characteristics of transit mixer delivery cycles

Parameter	Mean	Std. Dev	Minimum	Maximum
Average Hours per Trip	3.07	0.86	1.8	5.4
Trips per Day	4.83	1.12	3	7
Site Waiting Time (minutes)	34.5	12.7	10	65

Plants located in metropolitan areas such as Chennai and Coimbatore showed relatively higher operational durations due to traffic congestion and signalized intersections, whereas plants operating in industrial or semi-urban regions exhibited comparatively shorter delivery cycles. The variation in trip duration is summarized in Table 3, which presents the descriptive statistics of operational time parameters. The results indicate moderate variability in operational duration, suggesting that most deliveries occur within an

acceptable transportation window for maintaining concrete workability. The relationship between plant location and average operational time is illustrated in Figure 3, which compares the average trip duration across the surveyed RMC plants. The figure shows that plants located in dense urban corridors experience longer delivery cycles due to increased traffic congestion and higher site waiting times, while plants operating in industrial belts demonstrate shorter and more consistent transportation durations.

Figure 3. Average operational time per trip across surveyed RMC plants

The results indicate that operational time is influenced not only by transportation distance but also by site-level factors such as pump availability, labour coordination, and unloading efficiency. Extended waiting periods at construction sites increase engine idle time and contribute to additional fuel consumption and mechanical stress on mixer components. Consequently, improving coordination between batching plants and construction sites could significantly reduce delivery cycle time and enhance overall fleet productivity. Overall, the analysis demonstrates that while most RMC deliveries occur within acceptable operational limits, variations in urban traffic conditions and site readiness can significantly influence delivery efficiency. These

findings emphasize the importance of effective dispatch planning and improved site logistics in optimizing transit mixer operations.

3. Influence of Unloading Method on Delivery Efficiency

The method used for unloading ready-mix concrete at construction sites significantly influences the overall delivery cycle and operational efficiency of transit mixer fleets. During the field investigation, two primary unloading approaches were observed: manual chute unloading and pump-assisted unloading. Manual unloading typically involves labourers transferring concrete using wheelbarrows or buckets, whereas pump-assisted unloading utilizes mechanical concrete pumps to transport the material directly to the required location within the structure. These unloading practices differ considerably in terms of time efficiency and operational impact on the transit mixer. Analysis of the collected responses indicates that pump-assisted unloading considerably reduces the time required to complete a delivery cycle compared with manual unloading methods. The average unloading time recorded for pumping operations was approximately 28 minutes, whereas manual unloading required an average of 46 minutes, depending on site organization and labour availability. The descriptive statistics of unloading duration are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Comparison of unloading duration for different unloading methods

Unloading Method	Mean Time (minutes)	Std. Dev	Minimum	Maximum
Pump-Assisted	28	9	15	50
Manual Chute	46	14	25	75

The difference in unloading duration between the two methods is visually illustrated in Figure 4, which compares the distribution of unloading time for manual and pump-assisted operations as shown in Figure 4, manual unloading accounted for approximately 55% of delivery operations, while 45% of deliveries utilized pump-assisted unloading, indicating a balanced use of unloading technologies depending on project scale and site logistics.

Figure 4 Distribution of unloading methods used in RMC delivery operations

Extended unloading durations increase the idle running time of the transit mixer drum and engine, which may contribute to increased fuel consumption and additional mechanical stress on mixer components. Furthermore, longer unloading periods can reduce the number of trips a mixer can perform within a working day, thereby lowering overall fleet productivity. From an operational perspective, the adoption of pump-assisted unloading systems can therefore significantly enhance delivery efficiency and reduce operational delays in RMC transportation. The results highlight that unloading method is an important determinant of delivery cycle performance in the RMC supply chain. Improved coordination between batching plants and construction sites, along with the wider adoption of pumping equipment for larger construction projects, can substantially improve transportation efficiency and reduce operational downtime.

4. Maintenance Cost and Operational Reliability Analysis

Maintenance cost is a key indicator of the operational efficiency and reliability of transit mixer fleets used in ready-mix concrete transportation. The maintenance expenditure of transit mixers is influenced by multiple factors, including operational intensity, transportation distance, vehicle age, and breakdown frequency. To evaluate maintenance performance, descriptive statistics of key maintenance-related variables were analysed. The statistical summary of maintenance characteristics is presented in Table 5. The results show that the average monthly maintenance cost of transit mixers was approximately ₹27,850, with recorded values ranging between ₹14,000 and ₹46,000. The observed downtime averaged 13.92 hours per month, while the mean number of breakdown incidents was 1.28 per mixer, indicating moderate operational reliability across the surveyed fleets. In addition, the average vehicle age was 6.3 years, suggesting that most mixers were operating in mid-life operational conditions where maintenance requirements typically increase.

Table 5: Maintenance characteristics of transit mixer operations

Parameter	Mean	Std. Dev	Minimum	Maximum
Monthly Maintenance Cost (₹)	27,850	8,640	14,000	46,000
Downtime (hours/month)	13.92	5.74	5	28
Breakdown Incidents	1.28	0.92	0	4
Vehicle Age (years)	6.3	2.1	2	10

To determine whether maintenance cost varies significantly among the surveyed RMC plants, a one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was conducted. The ANOVA test examines whether the mean

maintenance cost differs significantly across plant locations. The results of the analysis are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: ANOVA results for maintenance cost across RMC plants

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	F-value	p-value
Between Plants	6.87×10^7	9	0.94	0.505
Within Plants	2.43×10^8	30	—	—

The obtained p-value (0.505) exceeds the significance threshold of 0.05, indicating that maintenance cost

differences between plant locations are not statistically significant. This suggests that

geographical location alone does not strongly influence maintenance expenditure. Instead, maintenance cost appears to be more strongly affected by operational conditions such as transportation distance, vehicle usage intensity, and equipment condition. To further examine the relationship between transportation conditions and maintenance expenditure, the association between kilometres travelled per trip and maintenance cost was analysed. The relationship is illustrated in Figure 5, which presents a scatter plot of transportation distance against maintenance cost.

Figure 5. Relationship between transportation distance and maintenance cost of transit mixers

The scatter distribution reveals a strong positive relationship between trip distance and maintenance cost, indicating that mixers operating on longer delivery routes experience higher mechanical wear and repair requirements. Increased travel distance results in longer engine operating hours, higher drum rotation cycles, and greater stress on hydraulic and

transmission components. Consequently, optimizing delivery routes and reducing unnecessary travel distances can significantly improve fleet efficiency and reduce maintenance expenditure. Overall, the combined descriptive analysis, ANOVA results, and scatter plot observations indicate that operational intensity and transportation distance play a dominant role in determining maintenance cost, while plant location itself has a relatively limited influence.

5. Reliability Assessment Using Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF)

The reliability of transit mixer fleets is an important factor influencing the continuity and efficiency of ready-mix concrete (RMC) transportation. Mechanical failures can disrupt delivery schedules, increase operational downtime, and lead to higher maintenance expenditure. Therefore, evaluating equipment reliability provides valuable insights into the performance and sustainability of transit mixer operations. In this study, the reliability of transit mixers was assessed using the Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF) metric, which represents the average operational duration between two consecutive equipment failures.

MTBF was estimated by analysing operational hours and recorded breakdown incidents obtained from the surveyed RMC plants. The calculated results indicate that the average MTBF of the observed transit mixer fleets was approximately 121.4 hours, with values ranging between 65 hours and 185 hours, as summarized in Table 7. These results indicate moderate reliability levels across the surveyed fleets and suggest that most transit mixers can operate continuously for several days before the likelihood of failure increases.

Table 7: Reliability indicators of transit mixer operations

Parameter	Mean	Std. Dev	Minimum	Maximum
MTBF (hours)	121.4	32.7	65	185
Breakdown Incidents	1.28	0.92	0	4
Downtime (hours/month)	13.92	5.74	5	28

To further illustrate reliability behaviour, a reliability function based on MTBF was developed using an exponential reliability model. The reliability function describes the probability that a system continues to operate without failure over a specified period of time. The resulting reliability curve is shown in Figure 6, which illustrates the probability of failure-free operation as operating time increases.

Figure 6. Reliability function of transit mixer operations based on MTBF.

As shown in Figure 6, the probability of uninterrupted operation gradually decreases as operating time increases. At the beginning of the operating cycle, the reliability value remains close to unity, indicating a high likelihood of failure-free performance immediately after maintenance or servicing. However, as operating hours accumulate, the reliability progressively declines due to mechanical wear and operational stress affecting critical components such as hydraulic motors, drum bearings, and transmission systems. The results emphasize the importance of preventive maintenance practices in maintaining high reliability levels for transit mixer fleets. Regular inspection schedules, lubrication programs, and timely replacement of worn components can significantly improve MTBF values and reduce unexpected failures. Improving reliability not only enhances equipment availability but also ensures smoother RMC delivery operations and minimizes delays in construction activities. Overall, the MTBF-based reliability analysis demonstrates that structured maintenance management and systematic monitoring of equipment performance are essential

for sustaining reliable transit mixer operations in RMC logistics systems.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the operational performance and maintenance reliability of transit mixers involved in ready-mix concrete (RMC) transportation across selected plants in Tamil Nadu. Based on the analysis of operational data and survey responses, the following key conclusions can be drawn:

1. The average transportation distance per delivery trip was approximately 15 km, with most RMC deliveries occurring within a 10–20 km operational service radius of batching plants.
2. The average delivery cycle duration was about 3 hours per trip, indicating that most concrete deliveries were completed within the acceptable operational time window required to maintain concrete workability.
3. The analysis of unloading practices showed that manual unloading accounted for approximately 55% of delivery operations, while pump-assisted unloading represented about 45%, demonstrating that unloading method selection depends largely on construction site conditions and project scale.
4. Maintenance performance analysis revealed that the average monthly maintenance cost of transit mixers was approximately ₹27,850, with observed values ranging between ₹14,000 and ₹46,000.
5. The ANOVA results indicated that maintenance cost differences among RMC plants were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$), suggesting that operational factors such as transportation distance, vehicle age, and usage intensity have greater influence on maintenance expenditure than plant location.
6. The scatter analysis demonstrated a positive relationship between transportation distance and maintenance cost, indicating that longer delivery routes contribute to increased mechanical wear and repair requirements.
7. Reliability evaluation using Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF) showed an average reliability

level of approximately 121 hours between failures, highlighting the importance of preventive maintenance in maintaining transit mixer fleet availability.

Overall, the study demonstrates that transportation distance, operational intensity, and maintenance practices are the key determinants of transit mixer operational performance and reliability in RMC logistics systems.

Research Limitations and future direction

Despite providing valuable operational insights, this study has several limitations. First, the analysis was based on data collected from a limited number of RMC plants within a single geographical region, which may not fully represent the operational characteristics of RMC logistics in other regions or countries. Second, the dataset primarily focused on operational and maintenance parameters and did not include detailed component-level failure data or long-term equipment lifecycle information. Third, external factors such as seasonal traffic variation, road conditions, and weather effects were not explicitly incorporated into the analysis, although they may influence transportation efficiency and equipment reliability. These limitations suggest that the results should be interpreted within the context of the studied region and operational conditions. Future research can expand this work by incorporating larger datasets from multiple regions to provide a broader understanding of RMC transportation systems. The integration of real-time telematics data from transit mixers, such as GPS-based trip monitoring and onboard sensor information, could enable more detailed analysis of operational performance and equipment health. In addition, advanced analytical approaches such as predictive maintenance models, machine learning algorithms, and reliability-based optimization techniques could be applied to improve failure prediction and maintenance scheduling. Further studies may also investigate route optimization and dispatch scheduling strategies to reduce transportation time and maintenance costs in RMC logistics. Such research would contribute to developing more efficient and data-driven fleet management systems for the construction industry.

1. Akboğa, Özge, and Selim Baradan. 2017. "Safety in Ready Mixed Concrete Industry: Descriptive Analysis of Injuries and Development of Preventive Measures." *INDUSTRIAL HEALTH* 55 (1): 54–66. <https://doi.org/10.2486/indhealth.2016-0083>.
2. Andika, Dimas Krisna, Stella Junus, and Esta Larossa. 2025. "Sistem Pemeliharaan Preventif Pada Peralatan Utama Stasiun Batching Plant Menggunakan Metode FMEA di PT. Azwa Utama Gorontalo." *Jurnal Teknik Industri Terintegrasi* 8 (3): 3284–89. <https://doi.org/10.31004/jutin.v8i3.47963>.
3. Bingöl, Befrin N., and David Arditi. 2025. "Supply Management System in Ready-Mixed Concrete Companies: Evidence from Turkey." *CIB Conferences* 1 (1). <https://doi.org/10.7771/3067-4883.1792>.
4. Chakraborty, Pranta, Muntasir Farhan, Shuvo Ranjan Das, and Debasish Sen. 2023. "INVESTIGATION ON PROPERTIES OF READY MIXED CONCRETE OVER TRANSIT TIME." *Malaysian Journal of Civil Engineering* 35 (2): 41–49. <https://doi.org/10.11113/mjce.v35.20289>.
5. Chaudhary, Ravi, Monika Saini, Ashish Kumar, and Kapil Kumar. 2025. "Reliability Characteristics Analysis of Ready-Mix Cement Plant under Classical and Bayesian Inferential Framework: A Comparative Analysis." *Brazilian Journal of Biometrics* 43 (3). <https://doi.org/10.28951/bjb.v43i3.790>.
6. Dönmez, Ozan Aykut, and Erdiñç Öner. 2024. "OPTIMIZING READY-MIXED CONCRETE TRANSPORTATION BY A TRUCK MIXER ROUTING MODEL FOR CONCRETE PLANTS." *Mühendislik Bilimleri ve Tasarım Dergisi* 12 (4): 802–20. <https://doi.org/10.21923/jesd.1445781>.
7. Ekawati, Yurida, Iddo Christian Sutrisno, and Teguh Oktiarso. 2024. "Tactical Activities to Improve the Effectiveness of Concrete Batching Plant Based on Overall Equipment Effectiveness Analysis." *Journal of Mechanical Engineering Science and Technology (JMEST)* 8 (2): 488. <https://doi.org/10.17977/um016v8i22024p488>.
8. Ferrari, Cristian, Nicolò Beccati, and Luca Magri. 2025. "Numerical Mixing Index: Definition and

REFERENCES

- Application on Concrete Mixer.” *Fluids* 10 (3): 72. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fluids10030072>.
9. Kabus, Oleksii, Larisa Butska, Olga Makarenko, Lidiya Pershina, and Andriy Tymoshchenko. 2018. “Evaluating the Efficiency of the Fluidity Retention of Ready-Mix Concrete during the Transportation of It to the Construction Site.” *MATEC Web of Conferences* 230: 03005. <https://doi.org/10.1051/mateconf/201823003005>.
 10. Kaitukov, Batraz Amurkhanovich. 2023. “Mechanization and Automation of the Process of Making Concrete Mixes.” *E3S Web of Conferences* 457: 01008. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202345701008>.
 11. Kresnadi, Daniel Mulyono, and Doddy Prayogo. 2021. “The Supply Chain Optimization of Ready Mix Concrete at PT X in Surabaya Using the Metaheuristic Method.” *Dimensi Utama Teknik Sipil* 8 (1): 35–48. <https://doi.org/10.9744/duts.8.1.35-48>.
 12. Mungase, Ashok P., and Pravin D. Nemade. 2025. “Optimized Management of a Sustainable Ready-Mix Concrete Batching Plant for High Grade Concrete Production.” *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology* 13 (2): 343–50. <https://doi.org/10.22214/ijraset.2025.66856>.
 13. Murthy, A. Ramachandra, P. K. Prasanna, G. Nipun, et al. 2024. “Analysing the Influence of Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag and Steel Fibre on RC Beams Flexural Behaviour.” *Scientific Reports* 14 (1): 4914. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-51164-x>.
 14. Novitskiy, Andriy, Oleksandr Banniy, Yuri Novitskiy, and Maxim Antal. 2023. “A Study of Mixer-Feeder Equipment Operational Reliability.” *Naukovij Žurnal «Tehnika Ta Energetika»* 14 (4): 101–10. <https://doi.org/10.31548/machinery/4.2023.101>.
 15. Saini, Monika, Ashish Kumar, and Dinesh Kumar Saini. 2025. “Reliability Analysis of Ready-Mix Concrete Plants Using MLE and Power Law Process.” *Discover Applied Sciences* 7 (7): 711. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-025-07319-0>.
 16. Siu, Francis Ming Fung, Anson Kwun Wang Wong, and Michael Anson. 2022. “Benchmarking Site-Plant Resource Matching Performance of Ready-Mixed Concrete Delivery and Placing.” *HKIE Transactions* 29 (1): 17–25. <https://doi.org/10.33430/V29N1THIE-2021-0021>.
 17. Weerapura, Vihan, Ranil Sugathadasa, M. Mavin De Silva, Izabela Nielsen, and Amila Thibbotuwawa. 2023. “Feasibility of Digital Twins to Manage the Operational Risks in the Production of a Ready-Mix Concrete Plant.” *Buildings* 13 (2): 447. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13020447>.

HOW TO CITE: Deivamani P.*, P. Subathra, Operational Performance And Maintenance Reliability Of Transit Mixers In Delivery Of Ready-Mix Concrete - An Empirical Study, *Int. J. Sci. R. Tech.*, 2026, 3 (4), 1183-1193. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19904596>